

A Study on Issue Objectives of IPOs: Indian Evidence

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ABSTRACT

Out of the many strategic decisions affecting the future of a company, decision to 'go public' or to launch Initial Public Offering (IPO) is one of the important decisions. Basic question in this regard is 'why do companies go public?' Immediate answer for this question appears to be raising capital when companies have greater growth opportunities. However, researchers across countries have found a number of many other reasons other than merely raising capital for companies' decisions to go for IPOs. Some of these notable reasons as to why companies go public include enhancing company reputation, motive to use IPO proceeds to acquire other businesses, market timing or cashing the 'windows of opportunity', desire of the promoters to become rich by divesting their stake at a time when their company is overvalued, to improve the cash position of the company, increased ability for the company to raise additional capital in future by enhancing liquidity for the retail investors, to use listed security as a currency to buy other businesses in future, and to use the decision to go public as a marketing tool through enhanced publicity after getting the company listed on the stock exchange.

The present study focuses on the issue objectives of the 76 IPOs that went public in India during the 2021 calendar year. The issue objectives in IPOs can be studied based on what type of shares are offered in the IPO – Fresh Issue (FI) or Offer for Sale (OFS). Fresh issue of shares is also called primary shares where the issue proceeds get added to the existing capital of the company. Offer for sale is called issue of secondary shares where proceeds from the issue of such shares do not get added to the existing share capital of the company; it will be taken away by some of the existing shareholders or promoters as part of disinvestment strategy. The present study found that out of 76 IPOs that went public during 2021, 17 IPOs consists of FI only, 14 IPOs consist of OFS only, and the remaining 45 IPOs consist of a combination of both FI and OFS. The total capital raised by these 76 IPOs amounted to Rs.1,30,300.58 crores; of these, Rs.52,111.56 crores was fresh issue, while Rs.78,189.02 crores was offer for sale.

Key words: Initial Public Offerings, Issue Objectives, Fresh Issue, Offer for Sale

1.INTRODUCTION:

When it comes to funding of organisations, initially it takes the form of seed capital that is usually provided by the promoters of the organisations and by their friends and relatives. Therefore, for most organisations, the early stage of their life is characterised by concentrated ownership or are featured by closely held shareholding pattern. If such organisations become successful in their early stage of life cycle, this success may motivate the promoters to launch the Initial Public Offerings (IPOs) of their firms. The first issue of equity shares of a company to the public is known as the Initial Public Offering. The launch of IPO by a company marks the transformation of it from closely held ownership pattern to widely held ownership pattern.

IPOs have been a significant source of mobilising long-term capital for most companies all over the world. It is not only the small and young firms that go for IPOs; even the big and

matured companies go for IPOs. Also, government-owned PSUs in different countries go for IPOs. However, apart from raising additional capital, IPOs also provide exit options to the promoters or other major investor groups of the IPO firms. Thus, IPOs serve the twin objective of either mobilising further capital needed for expansion and/or diversification of the organisation or enabling the current owners and investor groups to divest their stake in the company going for public issue. Accordingly, shares issued in an IPO could be of two types: Fresh Issue and Offer for Sale. Fresh issue of shares in an IPO means additional capital raised by the company which will get added to the existing share capital of the company. In other words, the outstanding share capital of the company will increase to the extent of amount raised by the issue of fresh issue of shares. On the other hand, when shares issued in an IPO belong to offer for sale category, the capital raised through these shares are taken away by the promoters or by the investor groups. Capital raised through this route will not get added to the existing share capital of the IPO firm.

The present paper is organised as follows: the first section provides the theoretical background of the concept of initial public offering and its objectives. The second section throws light on the previous works conducted by the researchers on the issue objectives of IPOs. The third section discusses research objectives. The fourth section discusses the sample, data and research methodology used in the study. The fifth section presents and discusses the findings of the study. The final section discusses about the conclusion.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

The various earlier works conducted in the area of issue objectives of IPOs can be summarised as under:

Reputation: Kadlec and McConnell (1994) have found that listing on prestigious stock exchange is a significant achievement for any company. Subrahmanyam and Titman (1999) noticed that after the IPO company gets listed, the stock exchange authorities regularly watch the activities of the company, investment analysts and media start reporting about the company, thus, there will be more and more information being published about the company. This will enhance the reputation of the company. As a result, getting experienced, talented and competent workforce becomes easier. Studying Italian IPOs, Ravasi and Marchisio (2003) found that apart from funds requirements IPO decision also enhances company reputation and, thus, its 'social capital'; company visibility, its prestige and the perceived trustworthiness of the company.

Acquisition: Brau and Fawcett (2006) find that the main objective behind IPO decision is to fund acquisition. On the contrary, the main reason for a firm not to go for public issue is to retain decision making power with the promoters. Also, Celikyurt et al. (2010) noted that desire of acquiring other companies is the main reason behind going public. They also found that acquisition after IPO is associated with further issue of equity and debt. Studying a sample of more than 400 acquisitions made in less than one year from IPO, Wiggens et al. (2007) found that these companies have witnessed positive valuation effects after announcing about their acquisition plans.

Market Timing: Pagano et al. (1998) noted that the reasons behind going public are not the raising of funds to meet future investments and growth; but, instead, it is the intention of the promoters to take benefit when stock market values similar firms high in the industry. Such a finding is consistent with the findings of Ritter (1984), Loughran et al. (1994) and Ljungqvist and Wilhelm (2002) who also documented concentration of IPOs based on market timing. Lowry (2003) also notes that apart from funds requirements, investor sentiment also has an important bearing on the number of IPOs coming to the market.

Liquidity: Mello and Parsons (1998) find that enhancing liquidity of the scrip through listing is a main factor behind the IPO decision of companies. Study also noticed that because of the

enhanced liquidity, cost of capital is lowered. According to Taulli (2000), shares listed on stock exchanges can also be used as collateral securities for loans. Helwege et al. (2007) studied insider ownership pattern of firms that went public in the US between 1970 and 2001. Study found that insider ownership held by officers and directors fell gradually after IPO; more than 50 percent of the firms included in the study had insider ownership of less than 20 percent after 10 years of IPO. This finding of Helwege et al. somewhat contradicts Pagano et al. (1998) who did not find strong evidence for portfolio diversification by IPO firms. The study found that promoters of IPO firms had divested only about 6 percent of their holding at the time of IPO and another 1.3 percent three years after IPO; they retain significantly more than a majority stake in such IPO firms.

Size of the Company: Pagano and Roell (1998) find that bigger companies can afford to incur the various issue related expenses and, therefore, are more likely to go for IPOs compared to small-sized companies. Ritter (1991) finds that IPO related expenses in the US are quite high because of which small firms find it difficult to go for IPOs. Pagano et al. (1998) found the probability of large-sized companies going for IPO is quite high; study also found that IPO companies are usually those which had grown much faster and had registered higher profitability just prior to IPO. The decline in profitability after IPO found by Pagano et al. (1998) is consistent with the findings of DeGeorge and Zeckhauser (1993), and Jain and Kini (1994).

Risk: Chemmanur and Fulghieri (1999) find that firms belonging to risky industries are more likely to issue IPOs because they want to diversify and also because the promoters want to divest their investments.

Loss of Confidentiality: Pagano et al. (1998) have found that companies with much intense focus on Research and Development activities usually do not want to share their information with outside agencies and, therefore, such companies are less likely to go for public issues.

Marketing Role: Demers and Lewellen (2003) studied the relationship between listing of securities and the sales records of the products of IPO companies. They found that higher underpricing (listing day closing price being significantly more than the issue price) leads to more publicity and marketing benefits which may take the form of press meets or resulting in more traffic in company website. However, Luo (2008) found that spending on pre-IPO marketing would help in reducing underpricing of IPOs and also that such spending would encourage IPO trading in the stock market.

Chemmanur and Fulghieri (1999) have found that firms which are in need of large amount of funds belonging to industries with too much technological uncertainties, are more likely to go for public issue of equity rather than private placement at a much early stage of their life cycle.

Examining what factors influence the IPO decision of companies in India, Mayur and Kumar (2007) found that size of the company, its age, profitability and leverage are the major factors influencing the IPO decision of companies in India. Their findings support the international findings by Pagano and Roell (1998) who found that bigger companies who can bear the high administrative and other executive costs associated with IPOs are more likely to go for public issue.

Ritter (1991) finds that younger but more profitable companies are more likely to go public. Such a finding of Ritter is consistent with Diamond (1991), Pagano and Roell (1998), and Chemmanur and Fulghieri (1999) who all find that even younger companies could overcome the problem of adverse selection if these companies have visible profitability.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The present study intends to study the following objectives:

- i) Amount of capital raised by the sample of IPOs in India during the study period
- ii) Of the total number of IPOs that came to the market during the study period, the number of IPOs with exclusive issue of fresh issue shares, with exclusive issue of offer for sale shares and the number of IPOs with a combination of both these
- iii) To know the amount of capital raised through the issue of fresh issue of shares, and through the issue of offer for sale shares
- iv) To study the different issue objectives: objectives when fresh issue of shares issued and when offer for sales shares are issued

4.SAMPLE, DATA AND METHODOLOGY:

The study focuses on the IPOs that came to the market in India during the calendar year 2021. The final offer documents of various IPOs belonging to 2021 are accessed from SEBI website. On examining, it was found that a total of 76 such IPOs came to the market in the year 2021.

In these offer documents, 'The Offer' or 'The Issue' section provides information as to, out of the total number of shares, how many 'Fresh Issue' shares and how many 'Offer for Sale' shares are offered in the IPO. This section also provides information about the amount of money raised by the issue of these two types of shares.

'The Offer' or 'The Issue' section of the offer document also provides details about the 'Equity Shares Outstanding prior to the Offer' and 'Equity Shares Outstanding after the Offer'. Study verifies whether 'Equity Shares Outstanding after the Offer' increases compared to 'Equity Shares Outstanding prior to the Offer' exactly by the number of 'Fresh Issue' shares issued in the IPO. In other words, if there is issue of "Offer for Sale" shares in an IPO, there would not be difference between equity shares outstanding before and after the IPO.

Study next examines the 'Objects of the Offer' section of the offer documents. This section provides the different objectives of the issue; separately for the issue of fresh issue of shares and for the issue of offer for sale shares. These objectives for each IPO are separately noted down.

5.FINDINGS OF THE STUDY:

On examining the 76 IPOs that went public in the Indian capital market during the calendar year 2021, study finds that of these 76 IPOs 17 IPOs had exclusively fresh issue of shares, 14 IPOs had exclusively offer for sale shares, and the remaining 45 IPOs had a combination of both fresh issue and offer for sale shares. That means, of the total number of IPOs that came to the market in India during 2021, 22.37 percent of them had only fresh issue shares, another 18.42 percent of the IPOs had offer for sale shares and the remaining 59.21 percent of them had a combination of both fresh issue and offer for sale shares.

The total amount of capital raised by all the 76 IPOs was Rs.1,30,300.58 crores. The amount of capital raised through the issue of fresh issue of shares was Rs.52,111.56 crores, while the amount of capital raised through the issue of offer for sale shares had been Rs.78,189.02 crores. This means, of the total amount raised through the issue of IPOs in India during the year 2021, 40 percent got added to the existing share capital of these companies; while the remaining 60 percent of the money raised was taken away by the promoters or existing investors of these companies.

The lowest amount of capital raised by any IPO, during 2021, through the issue of fresh issue of shares has been Rs.1.12 crores, while the highest amount of capital raised by the fresh issue of shares has been Rs.9,000 crores. The corresponding figures for the offer for sale category of shares issued have been Rs.1.50 crores and Rs.10,000 crores, respectively.

6. ISSUE OBJECTIVES:

The various objectives of the IPO issue are broadly categorised under two heads: issue objectives of IPOs where only offer for sale (disinvestment) shares are issued; and issue objectives of IPOs where fresh issue of shares, leading to the raising of additional capital, are issued.

The most striking issue objectives where the IPO consists of the issue of offer for sale share are as under:

- To achieve the benefits of listing of equity shares on a reputed stock exchange
- To enhance the visibility of the company and to build brand image for the products of the company
- Creating a public market for the equity shares of the company
- To enable the promoters, and the existing institutional investors of the company to divest their investments in the company

As far as issue objectives in an IPO consisting of the issue of fresh issue of shares are issued, study finds a variety of issue objectives. Some of these important objectives are as under:

- General corporate purposes which again include the followings:
 - ❖ To enhance liquidity of investment to the existing and also to the new investors
 - ❖ To brand the company and also to ensure better visibility for the company which may result in higher valuation, especially, for equity capital
- Repayment and/or prepayment of earlier loan taken either by the IPO company or by its subsidiaries, either fully or partially
- To fund the working capital requirements of the company
- Upgrading and/or expanding company's existing facilities which may the following forms:
 - ❖ To open new stores or outlets in different cities or locations
 - ❖ To upgrade R and D facilities of the company
 - ❖ To strengthen the distribution channels of the issuing company
 - ❖ To finance various capital expenditures and/or capital budgeting projects of the company
 - ❖ Expanding company's presence outside India; to set up manufacturing centre or distribution channel abroad
- To make investments in technology innovation, artificial intelligence (AI), and other organic growth initiatives
- To make investments in subsidiary companies in order to augment their capital base to facilitate their future growth
- To raise necessary funds required for strategic investments; to facilitate acquisition or takeover of other companies

7. CONCLUSION:

Companies in India consider the issue of IPOs as an effective vehicle for raising additional capital to meet their funds requirements for various reasons and also to divest the already invested capital of their promoters and/or institutional investors. Of the total number of IPOs that hit the capital market in India in the year 2021, 17 IPOs exclusively issued fresh issue of shares leading to the raising of additional capital; 14 IPOs issued exclusively offer for sale shares resulting in exit route or disinvestment for the promoters or existing investors.

Interestingly, vast majority of the remaining 45 out of the 76 IPOs that came to the market in 2021 issued a combination of both fresh issue and offer for sale shares. This means that out of the total funds raised through the issue of these IPOs, partial amount has been taken away by the promoters or existing investors in the companies; while the remaining amount got added to the share capital of the company.

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